

**XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI**
mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

**THE INFLUENCE OF PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT ON ACADEMIC
ACHIEVEMENT**

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Abstract. *Parental involvement is widely considered as the most crucial factor of children's academic achievement. Parental engagement has positive effects on children's academic achievement comprehensively. This study researches the various aspects of parental engagement and its impacts on children's academic success and attitudes towards learning. Attention of parents influences students' outcomes. Parents can aid their children by communicating with their teachers, participating in every meeting that is organized at their children's educational institutions or supporting with homework and projects. In addition, this article discusses how parents provide their children financially. For example, they can create an educational environment, purchasing all necessity and pay regularly for additional courses except for school lessons. Besides, parental engagement is an influencing aspect for students' academic success psychologically, such as motivating them, enhancing self-esteem, and social communication, as well as its role in fostering family cohesion and relationships between parents and children. Furthermore, the research gives some advice for parents how to assist their children in achieving academically. The study concludes by underscoring the vital and beneficial effects of different forms of parental engagement on students' educational upshot and emotional well-being.*

Keywords: *academic achievement, parental engagement, educational institutions, self-esteem, social communication, family cohesion, well-being.*

Introduction. Anne Henderson who is an Australian writer and deputy director of The Sydney Institute spoke about the influence of parental engagement on academic achievement and said: "Parental involvement is the most accurate predictor of a student's academic success!"

Parental engagement plays a significant role in students' educational results. Firstly, parents pay attention to their children in order to make them a professional and intelligent person. They organize a regular study routine by setting a consistent schedule for homework and study time which helps children to develop their good habits and time management skills. Limiting the distractions and setting boundaries on screen time and other interruptions during study hours ensures children's focus on their academic tasks. Besides, they take part in the appointments with the educators

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and converse with them about their children's studying, achievements, behavior, attendance and future jobs.

Parents give a hand to their children to succeed in education by doing the assignment together which is given at their educational institutions. Sharing ideas openly with children broadens their mind. Making the projects and presentations for various topics in collaboration improves children's creativity and sociability. As a result, parental engagement assists children to achieve success in education. Secondly, the impact of parental involvement on academic success can extend to pecuniary aspects. Considering the investment in education, such as tutoring services, extracurricular activities, and educational materials which can enhance a child's learning experience. Parents emphasize the importance of education, leading to higher aspirations for their children so they prefer masterful teachers for their children. The expenditure increases because of the environment that parents create for children. Parents also give their children networking opportunities so as to help them to achieve more. For example, if a student inhabits abroad due to study, his or her parents will make an attempt to support financially by purchasing all important resources, aiding to publish their initial article, thesis or book, and paying for the hired apartment. Expense of books that children need throughout studying is also vast. This is why the parents who intend to study their children work with more energy in order to make a big profit than others. In fact, parents provide their children exhaustively with financial assistance. Thirdly, parents' psychologically support for their children's academic success is really effective. The belief of parents encourages students to work more on themselves and it converts the attitude of a child into good sides. They motivate their children with the words that "You can do it!" and ordering children to do something that is special makes them independent. Making conversations will improve a child socially and this has a positive impact on enhancing family cohesion, such as how to talk with parents or siblings. In addition, reinforcing the value of effort and perseverance helps children to develop a growth mindset and resilience in the face of challenges. While it's important to promote high standards, ensuring that expectations are realistic and achievable, considering each child's abilities and interests will improve their skills of making decisions about job careers. Upbringing children by speaking with them like adults strengthens their leadership and independence. Parent's making good intentions with children and talking about their future successes inspires them to make an effort for their academic achievement.

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Suggestions. Parental engagement in education has been linked to outcomes for student achievements academically. This article offers some recommendations to parents about how to aid children to achieve their academic success.

- Knowing about children's interests. Parents should ask their children about their future jobs that stimulate them, as a result, children can be the most proficient and successful person in their spheres. The reason is that person makes an effort all the time so as to learn about the thing that is fascinating for them.

- Parent's active involvement in educational institutions. Participating in school activities and being aware of classroom happenings fosters a connection between home and school. In addition, children will make an attempt to study hard and spend time efficiently if their parents observe them. Besides, children attend schools and take part in all lessons by being active.

- Explaining about how to manage time. Parents ought to teach their kids how to plan their days. This helps them not to waste valued time and become a punctual person all the time. The person who spends time usefully manages to perform everything that is arranged.

- Limiting the screen time. Parents should restrict the time that children spend on phones, laptops or television since it is harmful for children to use them most of the time. They may encounter the loss of eyesight or they are likely to watch something which is not advantageous for them. Otherwise, parents should mention that they can watch the movies or videos that advance their study and behavior.

- Doing physical activities: Sometimes parents tend to make their kids learn more by doing their assignments which belong to mental abilities. On the other hand, this leads to sedentary life so doing physical activities such as jogging or riding a bicycle may be effective for children's health.

- Purchasing books. Buying the suitable and captivating books will be beneficial for children to gain more knowledge. This is why parents ought to give a book to their children which is appropriate for their age and field. Besides, this can broaden their worldwide.

- Additional courses: Parents should organize some courses for their children apart from school lessons. This may develop their education in various subjects and it will have a positive effect on children's mind if it relates to foreign languages. Throughout this period, the ability of leadership will develop straightforwardly.

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•Celebration of achievements. Even though it is small, every academic success should be celebrated by parents. As a consequence, children are motivated by this kind of events and presents. Do not blame children if it does not bring success because sometimes it belongs to destiny or luck. Because there is a lot to study and learning is lifelong journey.

Overall, parental involvement plays the key role in students' academic success. Therefore, if parents control and pay attention regularly to their children, they will try hard to work on themselves.

Conclusion. To sum up, the importance of parental involvement and implementing strategies to encourage and support parents' active participation in their children's education foster academic excellence, and create pathways to success for all students. Parents worry about their children's behavior, confidence, directorship, and future profession so they provide them financially and mentally. Each parents desire that their children will be a competent so parental involvement can be a culprit for becoming a perfect person. The communication between parents and children motivates kids to be the best among their peers in all sectors.

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